

평화를 무시하는 북한의 호전성과 지정학

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이 글은 네루대학에서 정치학 박사학위를 한 마힌드라 교수가 쓴 글로 북한의 호전성에 대하여 그 지정학적인 원인이 무엇인가 분석하고 있다. 인도의 학자들은 한반도 문제나 북핵 상황에 대하여 비교적 아웃사이드의 입장에서 객관적인 아이디어를 제공한다. 마힌드라 교수는 김정은 시대 이후 북한의 핵실험과 미사일 시험에 대하여 분석하면서 결국 대화를 재개하는 것만이 문제를 해결할 수 있다고 주장한다.

BELLIGERENT NORTH KOREA AND GEOPOLITICS: PEACE DEFIED

The instability in the East Asia over the past years and since the discontinued Six Party Talks in 2009, has obstructed the peace process, and affected the geopolitics in the region. Actions of North Korea led to the formation of strategic allies of Japan, South Korea (Republic of Korea - ROK) and United States (US) to response the emerged situation. Nonetheless, North Korea (Democratic Republic of Korea-DPRK), moved forward by being more aggressive after power shifted to its new

supreme leader, Kim Jong Un, who advanced the military capabilities significantly inconsistent to its size and economy by improving military technology and testing the weapons. North Korea has followed the same agenda, as the previous leader and father of Kim Jong Un shaped the military strategies. The missile testing and nuclear development program has caused a threat directly to its neighbors and secondarily to the US.

Historically, to control the Korean Peninsula by

imperialist forces before and after the World War II, has witnessed the confrontations. Actually Korean Peninsula (area of 85,270 sq mi), has always been a significant strategic location, and the target to control the peninsula, was one of the major fight to dictate the Asian region, especially around the East Asia. For the geopolitical interests, several direct clashes took place to dominate the Korean Peninsula, and the peninsula has observed history of wars in between China-Japan, Russia-Japan and US-China, helping numerous strategic determinations and historic arrangements. Geostrategic position of peninsula has attracted the great powers for geopolitical influence (Pratt, 2007). More than five thousand years, peninsula of Korea was unite until the foreign geopolitical interest divided the identical descent of Korean people in 1953, splitting each other with a political and geographic boundary. The settlement of 1953, not only created the Korean Demilitarized Zone (DMZ) to separate the two nations, nonetheless, berth of North and South Korea are theoretically at the state of war and competing to inflate their military competence.

The containment approach is active in the region with 28,500 US military personnel? stationed in South Korea. US army is not only protecting South Korea, however valuable missile defense base of US military inhibition is a strategy against the People's Republic of China (PRC). South Korea might be capable of protecting itself from North Korean aggression, nevertheless, US continuously bearing the security assurance

(Chung, 2008). The defense expenditure of South Korea is more than the annual GDP of North Korea. Conversely, US military is equipped with Rocket Launching and Missile defense system, transportation and other form of precious military capabilities in the peninsula. All the same, China has similar strategic concerns in North Korea and Chinese government qualms that the uncertainty in Pyongyang (capital of North Korea), might be the direct effect on its security. China is against of consistent US military movements on the border, and strategically attempts to preserve North Korea for future safety standpoints.

The recent development from North Korea military aggression has escalated tension in the region yet again. In 2012, the long range ballistic missile tests (Taepodong-2) by North Korea, has challenged its neighbors. The low grade satellite rocket based launch of Unha-3 (based on Taepodong-2 technology) from Sohae site, was successful in December 2012. This successful launch has proved that the country has the skill to launch a two or three-stage ballistic missile with an adequate range to hit targets up to 4,000-6,000 km long distance and it appeared that the Pyongyang decided to share the technology to Iran (US urged to block, 28 January 2016). South Korean and the US authorities conducted an inspection of components of the launched rocket after first stage subsequent to its separation, plunged into the Philippines sea ocean during the launch in December 2012.

North Korea used the four Rodong missile

(associated with the Soviet R-17-Scud-B missile) engines for the first stage booster and used another Scud missile engine to carry out the second stage to save cost and time. Another interesting assessment emerged from analysis of the data and subsequent simulations, the missile, North Korea has tested, appeared to have a range of 10,000 km and have potential to carry a warhead weighing 500 kilograms. The December 2012 launch, provides facts that the launch succeeded due to advance technology used in the rocket and missiles (Fact Sheet, 2012).

The missile capacity of North Korea continued and progressing, which is certainly a tense situation in the East Asian region, and the successful test of a Taepodong missile through all three stages proves that North Korea had the capability of an intercontinental ballistic missile (ICBM) technology and undoubtedly it succeeded (North Korea Successfully, 2013). These acquired advanced military technology is one the main tension and certainly a change in the geopolitical status of the region. After the power transferred to Kim Jong Un, there has been several progresses in the military capacity of North Korea. The third underground nuclear test was conducted in February 2013, and South Korean Ministry of National Defense specified the blast of six to nine kilotons based on Comprehensive Test Ban Treaty (CTBT) organization calculation methods. Numerous collection methods were positioned by the US, Japan and South Korea to classify and describe the test. Nonetheless, there is no proof,

whether the test was based on plutonium or highly enriched uranium- HEU (Choi, February 2013). The test has posed danger to its neighbors, Japan and South Korea, these countries are militarily depend on the ally, US.

Furthermore, North Korea continues to advance both its nuclear and missile programs under the Kim Jong-un command, and it has actively established and continued its ballistic missile force including its nuclear competences, it has not neglected its conventional military forces as well. North Korea has included hundreds of new army tanks to its military after 2005 with advanced fire control system (Eun-jung, 2013). In 2013, the US Department of Defense, reported to Congress stating that efforts of North Korea to upgrade its conventional weapons is continuing and it has reinforced long range weaponry technologies adjoining the DMZ. These advance long range weapons could attack at several targets in Japan and South Korea. Approximately 7,000 highly trained Special Operation Force (SOF) and ballistic missiles being maintained for future military counter offense by North Korea towards its neighbor, South Korea (Department of Defense, 2012). Additionally, the cyber combat of the North Korean military is highly sophisticated and computer hackers are trained to launch cyber-infiltration and cyber-attacks as well. And, in March 2013, South Korean government has reportedly confirmed that North Korea was behind the massive cyber-attack that was conducted against financial firms and broadcasting

corporation (Lee, March 2013).

The recent nuclear test (probably Hydrogen bomb) on Punggye-ri test site in early of January 2016, as announced by the media of North Korea, unquestionably a challenge for the international community against nuclear arm free world. North Korea is banned from testing nuclear weapons under United Nations Security Council (UNSC) resolutions (North Korean carries, January 2016). Nonetheless, this nuclear experiment by North Korea highlights that the country would continue on its policy of both building up its nuclear weapons and developing its economy correspondingly. And, it also disclosed that North Korea would not multiply nuclear weapons to other countries. The statement repeated that North Korea would not dismantle its nuclear weapons program unless the US would change its opposed idea towards it.

Internationally, the underground nuclear test by North Korea has been condemned soon after the test was conducted and surfaced in the media. South Korea and US called it the terror act and blamed that the activities are against the ongoing peace process in the East Asia. One month later, again North Korea launched a low orbit earth observation satellite, Kwangmyongsong-4(Bright Star-4), in February 2016, based on the same Unha carrier rocket launch technology (Brunstrom, February 2016). This too was criticized by South Korea and the US, later, both the countries admitted to counter North Korea by installing the

Terminal High Altitude Area Defense (THAAD) - advanced missile defense system, in South Korea, which was strongly opposed by Russia (Power, February 2016).

January 2016 incident and rocket based missile testing, has change the geopolitical situation at large (Beijing Says, 07 April 2016). The East Asian region is economically advance and comparably better than other Asian parts. North Korean belligerent activities in the region is not suitable for peace, and is against the international norms. Despite the sanctions, treaties and international pressure, the test was conducted. In March 2016, UNSC adopted severer sanctions against North Korea, and this advanced the replicated nearer cooperation between the US and China on a longstanding dispute as well. The 15-members of the Council approved a resolution, negotiated after many days by US and Chinese officials, that all cargo going in and out of North Korea must be inspected, all weapons trade must be banned and expand the list of individuals, who are under the purview of sanctions. These sanctions on North Korea, would surely help the East Asia to maintain its peace and security.

Lastly, the geopolitical strategy either by the US, Japan, China, South Korea or by North Korea, is significantly important for both the North and South divide. North Korea would continue its tests for the advancement of military capabilities, because it has only state of affairs left with it. These activities boosts the confidence level in the

people and the leaders of North Korea, and sometime it gain the sympathy from the likeminded countries also. Globally, North Korea could claim its position being a hard-hitting nation. Nonetheless, the acts of North Korea is not a solution to the problem that exists in the region.

However US, Japan, China and South Korea have to decide that how they would like to deal with belligerent North Korea. Peace building process through resuming talks and accord could bring the solution of the existing problems in the East Asia.

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조·일7년전쟁, 한국전쟁 그리고 베트남전쟁

근·현대사의 3대 전쟁 분석과 국가안보현실 진단

전쟁은 폭력을 국가 간에 공공연히 교환하는 행위로서 이 보다 더 위험하고 종대한 국사는 없다. 지난날 우리가 치른 이들 전쟁의 교훈은 결코 공짜로 얻어진 것이 아니다. "FREEDOM IS NOT FREE"란 명언이 이를 대변해 주고 있다. 인간이 극한적인 상황 하에서 목숨을 담보로 국가를 위해 전장에서 적과 싸운 참전용사들의 고귀한 정신을 신세대들이 이해하고 수용하게 될 때, 국가안보에 대한 부정적 사고와 왜곡된 시각은 정상화 시정될 수 있을 것으로 믿는다. 진정한 평화는 평화유린세력을 제압 가능한 능력과 의지가 있어야 보장된다.

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